

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 16, No. 9

Dear J.UCS Readers,

For the first time this year this is an issue where all six papers have at least one European author, indeed European authors are dominating. Thus, the geographical spread is less than usual, but the spread in topics is as wide as ever! Hence everyone should be able to find something interesting to study.

I'd like to take this opportunity to thank all reviewers involved in the evaluation of the papers of this issue for their work. Without their dedication and willingness to use a part of their valuable time to evaluate submissions, read the revised versions and guide and support authors to improve their work, with no other reward than a thanks on our part, it would not be possible to present you this issue. Happy reading!

To make this issue particularly interesting we will insert on the second page of every paper a video-clip from the Soccer World Cup in South Africa. We hope this will encourage you to open each paper, yet you will find it won't distract you too much.

Also, don't forget to register for the first conference of the Academia Europaea (www.ae-info.org) in which all editors of J.UCS have also been involved. For the excellent program see http://www.ae-info.org/ae/Acad_Main/News/AIECS_2010.

Hope to see many of you in Graz at this meeting!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Dr. H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
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PS: You did not find the videos on page 2 of each paper? Well, forgive me this little silly joke! But we're working on it ...